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Evaluation of Catchment Afforestation Potentials of Seedlings of Three Native Tree Species under Different Soil Moisture Conditions

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Abstract

*In many parts of the world, key water catchments and watershed ecosystems have been degraded by successive waves of anthropogenic activities, thus requiring rehabilitation. One of the drawbacks of rehabilitation of degraded catchments is the lack of information about species suitable to local conditions. This study was designed to evaluate the catchment afforestation/reforestation potentials of three native tree seedlings under different moisture levels. In a complete randomised design (3 species x 4 treatments x 12 replicates) in a shade house, 144 pots with fairly uniform actively growing seedlings of *Markhmia tomentosa*, *Funtumia Africana* and *Prunus Africana* were treated to 4 soil moisture levels, corresponding to 12.5, 25, 50 and 100% field capacity determined gravimetrically. Growth parameters (collar diameter, height and number of leaves) were measured fortnightly, while leaf area, biomass components and their derivatives were measured destructively after six months of growth. The seedlings' rate of transpiration and evapotranspiration ($\text{gH}_2\text{O/s/m}^2$) were determined gravimetrically and water-use efficiency derived (g/L). The general effects of the soil moisture capacity on the growth performances were significantly different at $P < 0.001$. *Markhmia tomentosa* showed maximum leaf number (42) and leaf area (10712.8 cm^2 , 25% treatment), collar diameter (17.8 cm) and root shoot ratio (2.8, 50% treatment). *Funtumia africana* at 50% soil moisture capacity showed maximum height (88.6 cm) and total biomass (60.3g). *Prunus africana* had the least growth performances. *Markhmia* had the maximum rate of transpiration ($12.69 \text{ gH}_2\text{O/s/m}^2$), evapotranspiration ($14.20 \text{ gH}_2\text{O/s/m}^2$). *Funtumia* gave the best water-use efficiency (176.5 ml/g). Their least values were observed in *P. Africana*. *Funtumia africana* had the best water use efficiency while *Markhmia tomentosa* had the best root development. These two species would be suitable for the afforestation/reforestation of water catchment areas in Cameroon at low altitude while *P. africana*, naturally adapted to high altitudes require further investigations.*

Key words: Water catchment, reforestation/afforestation, tree seedlings, growth parameters, transpiration, evapotranspiration and water-use efficiency

1. INTRODUCTION

Good water quality and quantity are necessary for the enhancement of ecological stability and diversity, and both play important roles in maintaining sustainable agricultural, economic development and human health (Lei *et al.*, 2022, Antolini *et al.*, 2020, ; Singh *et al.*, 2017 Lu *et al.*, 2015). The water resources dynamics within a catchment are governed by a combination of climate and land use (Wagner *et al.*, 2018 and Farjad *et al.*, 2017), although other catchment characteristics such as topography, soil and lithology are important, they

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do not change over short time periods (Lei *et al.*, 2022). There is a direct correlation between land use/land cover and climate (GLOWS-FIU, 2014). Land use/land cover change alter the natural ecosystem services by modifying the ecological structure and functions, influencing human demand for ecosystem services and affecting its ability to provide ecosystem services to human (Sonter *et al.*, 2017). Deforestation is the main driver of land cover change and climate change with sustainable water availability in quantity and quality being a major consequence. Trees and water are inseparable and the former is well known for its regulating function in water catchment areas (Brook *et al.*, 2008).

Highland regions act as water catchment and serve as the main hydropower generation source, provides water resources for agricultural, industrial, and domestic use downstream (Razali *et al.*, 2018 and Roozitalab *et al.*, 2013). Land degradation, the decline in the natural quality of the soil component within an ecosystem is often signalled by a decrease in vegetation cover and the capacity of a watershed to store water (Narulita *et al.*, 2008; Mawardi, 2010; Eni, 2012). Trees are seriously threatened by forest exploitation; habitat loss and fragmentation; invasive species introduction; land cover change as a consequence of demographic explosions and the quest for arable land (Malcom *et al.*, 2007; Wright *et al.*, 2006; MINFOF, 2005). Remedies so far include ratifying recommendations of conferences such as the Montreal Conference of Parties Meeting of the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in late 2005. So far, the conference point on Clean Development Mechanism-afforestation reforestation (CDM-AR) projects have received growing attention in mitigating climate change and water resource depletion by avoiding unnecessary deforestation and encouraging reforestation and afforestation (Lawrence *et al.*, 2007; Gullison *et al.*, 2007; Mollicone *et al.*, 2007; Tavoni *et al.*, 2007).

In the western highlands of Cameroon (West and North West regions) and the Adamawa plateaux, key water catchment habitats and watershed ecosystems have been destroyed by successive waves of cultural activities such as slash/burn agriculture, bushfire, pesticides, and settlement expansion due to population growth (Ndenecho, 2009). Equally, vegetation has often been burnt or cleared, exposing the soils and streams to the full strength of solar radiation and erosion in these regions. These anthropogenic influences result in active stream and gully erosion affecting water courses in the water catchment areas, damaging landscape ecostructures and water catchment processes that manage flows, yields, reliability and quality of water resources (Egbe *et al.*, 2013).

Earlier afforestation and reforestation efforts in these regions saw the introduction of alien invasive species of eucalyptus with great economic potentials for these grassland areas. Not only did the trees provide the much needed fuel wood, the young poles were used in the construction of local houses, matures poles for electricity transport lines and the huge old trees provided timber for furniture and roofing house in the towns. The environmental consequences of using the wrong species for reforestation have been huge, one being the exacerbation of water crises over time. The impact of the mismanagement of tree-water relationship presents adverse effects on local livelihood. This includes the time to search for good quality water and conflict of ownership (Ndenecho, 2009).

In recent years, there have been tremendous efforts in Cameroon to afforest or reforest many areas as a management strategy to combat desertification, climate change and water crises. One of the drawbacks of developing plants for the rehabilitation of degraded catchments is the lack of information about species suitable to local conditions (Auliyani *et al.*, 2019). This suggests that research on indigenous trees to identify the trees species that are capable of protecting water catchment areas would further add impetus to the current drive for afforestation/reforestation of water catchment areas. Growth, biomass allocation, rate of transpiration and water use efficiency of trees provide important clues on which tree species are suitable for the afforestation of water catchment areas (Egbe *et al.*, 2013). The adoption of good strategies in water catchment management is therefore indispensable, yet requires significant research. This study compared the effect of different soil

moisture levels on the early growth performance, rate of transpiration and water use efficiencies of three native tree seedlings (*Markhmia tomentosa*, *Funtumia africana* and *Prunus africana*) as an assessment of their suitability for reforestation/aforestation of water catchment areas in Cameroon.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study site

This study was carried out in the screen house of the Department of Botany and Plant Physiology, University of Buea. This area is located in the Southwest Region of Cameroon between latitude $3^{\circ}57^1$ to $4^{\circ}27^1$ N and longitude $8^{\circ}58^1$ to $9^{\circ}25^1$ E. Buea is located on the eastern slope of Mount Cameroon. It has a mean annual rainfall of about 2800 mm, received mostly between June and September (Egbe *et al.*, 2013). The mean annual temperature, mean relative humidity and sunshine are 28.0, 86% and 900 to 12000 hours per annum respectively. Buea is mountainous with thick evergreen forest vegetation at the lower elevations and transitional changes along altitudinal gradient. Agriculture is the major activity in this region and this is done mostly by shifting cultivation and organized commercial plantations by Cameroon Development Cooperation (CDC) (Egbe *et al.*, 2011).

2.2 Study species

Funtumia africana (Benth.) Stapf is an Apocynaceae that can reach 30 m in height with a straight, cylindrical trunk and a narrow tree crown (Orwa *et al.*, 2009). It is also common in forest regrowth. It is a native tree of Angola, Cameroon, Ivory Coast, Democratic Republic of Congo, Gabon, Kenya, Liberia, Mozambique, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Tanzania, Togo and Uganda. The flowers are yellow-white with fragrant dense cymes. The tree is used for timber and has other cultural importance such as drum making (Omino *et al.*, 1993). It is also used in erosion control, fuel wood, apiculture, production of gum or resin, treatment of urinary incontinence and burns, adherent for poisoned arrows, soil fertility improver of the surrounding, and extraction of alkaloids such as funtumine and funtumidine that are hypotensive (Orwa *et al.*, 2009).

Prunus africana (Hook. f.) Kalkman is a Rosaceae that attains a height of 30 m with a straight bole and simple, alternately arranged leaves (Simpson, 2006). It is restricted to montane and afro-montane forest habitats in Africa and parts of U.S.A. Biophysically, it grows best limited between 900-3400 m altitudes, 890-2600 mm mean annual rainfall and 18-26°C mean annual temperature. The flowers are small, creamy white and fragrant. *Prunus africana* flowers between November and February. The plant is used for timber, apiculture, erosion control, fuel wood and soil improver through mulching. The bark extracts contain phytosterols (β - Sitosterol, β -sitostenone) used to treat benign prostate hyperplasia (BPH) (Orwa *et al.*, 2009).

Markhmia tomentosa (Benth.) K. Schum. is a Bignoniaceae that attains a height of 15 m with a straight often branched bole and compound bipinnate leaves. It is widely distributed through savanna forests in West and Central Africa extending southward to Angola (Simpson, 2006). Biophysically, it is limited between 400-1000 m altitudes. The tree produces large yellow flowers in long terminal racemes. Its peak of flowering in Cameroon is between March and May. It is used as an ornamental, tanning, timber; treatment of skin diseases, sores and scabies; oedema of the legs and elephantiasis, and rheumatic pain. Tannins and astringents have been extracted from its leaves (Orwa *et al.*, 2009).

2.3 Methods

2.3.1 Growth performance of the seedlings of the three tree species under four soil moisture levels.

Seeds of *Funtumia africana*, and *Markhmia tomentosa* *Prunus africana* were collected from local stands in the North West region of Cameroon. The seeds were sown in seed boxes in the shade house of the University of Buea. After germination, the seedlings were transplanted into polythene pots measuring 12.5 cm diameter by 25

cm high, filled with topsoil. All the transplanted seedlings were allowed to establish for four weeks, time enough for the shoots to develop new leaves while in the pots before application of the various treatments.

The soil moisture capacity of the pots was determined gravimetrically using five randomly selected pots from those filed for seedling transplant. These pots were watered to saturation and allowed to stand for three hours to allow water in the soil macro-pores to drain completely by gravity. The soil at field capacity of each pot was weighed and oven dried at 105⁰C to constant weight in an air flow oven (Gallenhamp Hotbox). The soil moisture at field capacity was determined as the difference between the mass of soil at field capacity and that of oven dried soils and the mean value calculated. Soil moisture levels (25, 50, 100 and 200ml) were determined as 12.5, 25, 50 and 100% of the soil moisture at field capacity.

144 pots (48 of each species) with fairly uniform actively growing seedlings were treated to the different soil moisture levels. The experiment was a completely randomized design (4 treatments x 12 replicates) and the seedlings were placed in a screen house to mimic understory conditions in the forest. The pots were watered three times weekly with the various volumes of stream water flowing not far from the shade house. The water levels of 12.5, 25 50 and 100% of the soil field capacity mimicked the soil water potential levels recorded in tropical regions during different phases of the dry and rainy seasons (Martinez-Berdeja *et al.*, 2008).

Initial measurements of growth parameters were taken by non-destructive method and subsequent measurements were carried out at 14 days intervals for a total duration of 6 months. The parameters included collar diameter, measured using an electronic veneer calliper (Shenzhen® G02022615) to the nearest 0.1 mm; height was measured from a point at the soil surface to tip of terminal bud with a metre rule to the nearest 0.1 cm and fully open leaves were counted. At the end of the experiment, the seedlings roots were carefully removed from the pot and washed with tap water repeatedly to remove all the soil particles and first order lateral roots counted. The length of tap root was measured with a metre rule. The seedlings were partitioned into roots, stems and leaves and their fresh weights recorded with an electronic balance (Ohaus Scout TM Pro) to the nearest 0.01g. These were oven dried to constant weight at 70⁰C and dry weight recorded. Leaf area was measured with a leaf area meter (Orsenigo 121TM35) to the nearest 1.0 cm². Leaf area ratio (LAR), leaf mass fraction (LMF), stem mass fraction (SMF), root mass fraction (RMF), specific leaf area (SLA), specific stem length (SSL) and root shoot ratio (RSR) were determined (Boor and Grub, 2003).

2.3.2 Evaluation of the rate of transpiration, evapotranspiration and water-use efficiencies of the tree seedlings

36 potted seedlings (12 per species) at six months were selected and the pots watered to saturation, allowed to drain completely of gravitational water for three hours. Six of the 12 pots with seedlings for each species were covered with black polythene bags from the bottom of each pot to the soil surface of the pots to prevent evaporation of water from the soil surface, while the remainder were not covered. The potted seedlings with soil moisture at field capacity were weighed using an electronic balance (Scout TM Pro) and placed in an open environment (100% light). The weights of the pots were noted at 30 minutes intervals for 6 hours (10 am to 4 pm) each day for three days. The rate of transpiration/evapotranspiration was determined by the gravimetric method. Light intensity was measured at 30 minutes intervals using a photo detector luxmeter (MASTECH ® MS6610). Data on relative humidity was obtained from Cameroon Development Co-operation (CDC) meteorological Centre in Tiko which is about 12 km from Buea and is the closest weather station.

The rate of transpiration and evapotranspiration for each square meter of leaves of species were calculated from equation (1).

$$\xi = \left\{ \frac{w_i - w_f}{t_f - t_i} \right\} \times \frac{TLA}{10000} \quad (1)$$

Where, ξ = rate of transpiration or rate of evapotranspiration as appropriate. W_i and W_f were masses measured at an initial time t_i and after a given time lapse, t_f respectively. TLA= Total leaf area of the seedling measured. Changes in masses were plotted against time and the line of best fit was obtained. The gradient of the slope was calculated and this gave the transpiration rate.

Water-use efficiency was calculated as volume (ml) of water needed to produce 1g of biomass. This was calculated using the equation (2) (Jones, 2004).

$$WUE = 1 / (TDB / TW) \quad (2)$$

Where, WUE = Water use efficiency of the tree seedlings, TDB = Total dry biomass (g) and TW = Total water used (ml) in the experiment and this was 9.6 liters in six months, only for seedlings supplied with 200 ml soil moisture level.

Data analyses

The resulting data were tested for normality and homogeneity. Analyses of Variance were carried out on the resulting data using GENSTAT statistical package version 14.0 to test the effects of the different treatments on plant growth parameters, biomass allocation, rate of transpiration and water use efficiency. Comparisons were done using the least square differences (LSD) of means. Tables and graphs were drawn using the Microsoft Office Excel 2007

3. RESULTS

3.1 The effects of soil moisture levels on the patterns of growth in heights, collar diameters and leaf number

The growth trends with respect to collar diameter, heights and the number of leaves showed that there were significant variations (at $P= 0.05$) between the species and treatments. Seedlings supplied with 50 and 100% soil moisture capacities showed sharp increases in the growth pattern of heights for all the tree species from the 10th week after treatment application (Figure 1). *Funtumia africana* and *Markhmia tomentosa* seedlings showed a sharp increase in collar diameter from 8 weeks after treatment application while the growth pattern of collar diameter of *Prunus africana* remained constant regardless of the treatment and time factor in the course of the study (Figure 2). *Markhmia tomentosa* and *Funtumia africana* seedlings showed marked increase in the number of leaves from the 4th and 6th weeks respectively after treatment application in all the treatments (Figure 3).

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Figure 1. Growth patterns of heights of the seedlings of three tree species supplied with four soil moisture levels.

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Figure 2. Growth patterns of collar diameter of the seedlings of three tree species under four moisture levels.

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Figure 3. Growth patterns of the number of leaves of the seedlings of three tree species under four soil moisture levels.

3.2 The effects of soil moisture levels on morphological characters of seedlings of the three native tree species.

The effects of the treatments on the heights and number of leaves of the species were significant different at $P \leq 0.001$ (Table 2). The 50, 25 and 100% soil moisture levels recorded the highest heights (88.6, 62.0 and 55.7 cm)

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for *F. africana*, *M. tomentosa* and *P. africana* seedlings respectively. The least heights for *F. africana* and *M. tomentosa* were 49.0 and 46.7 cm and these were observed in seedlings supplied with 12.5% soil moisture level. The least height for *P. africana* seedlings was 31.1 cm recorded in seedlings supplied with 50% soil moisture capacity.

The effects of the treatments on the collar diameter of the species were significantly different at $P \leq 0.001$ (Table 2). The seedlings of species treated with 100% soil moisture level or at field capacity recorded the highest collar diameters of 17.8, 11.3 and 4.3 cm for *Markhmia tomentosa*, *Funtumia africana* and *Prunus africana* respectively. The *F. africana* and *M. tomentosa* seedlings treated with 12.5% soil moisture capacity gave the least collar diameters of 7.9 and 9.5 cm respectively while in the *Prunus africana* seedlings treated with 50% soil moisture capacity recorded the least collar diameter of 3.4 cm.

The highest number of leaves for *Funtumia africana* and *Markhmia tomentosa* seedlings were 31 and 42 and these were recorded in the seedlings supplied with 50 and 25% soil moisture levels respectively. The least number of leaves (13) for *Prunus africana* was recorded in seedlings treated to the 100% soil moisture level (Table 2).

The effects of the treatments on the leaf area and specific leaf area showed significant variations at $P \leq 0.02$ (Table 2). The largest leaf areas (5213.0, 10712.8 and 369.7 cm² for *F. africana*, *M. tomentosa* and *P. africana* seedlings) were observed in the 50, 25 and 100% soil moisture levels respectively. Their least leaf areas (912.7, 3233.1 and 116.0 cm² for *F. africana*, *M. tomentosa* and *P. africana* seedlings) were recorded in 12.5, 100 and 12.5% soil moisture levels respectively. The leaf area ratio was highly significantly different for all the tree species. The highest leaf area ratios for *Markhmia tomentosa* and *Prunus africana* seedlings were 267.1 and 107.6 cm²/g and this was noted in seedlings supplied with 25% soil moisture capacities while the highest leaf area ratio for *Funtumia africana* seedlings was 86.5 cm²/g recorded in seedlings supplied with 50% soil moisture level. The least leaf area ratios for *F. africana* and *P. africana* seedlings were 58.7 and 94.9 cm²/g respectively and were observed in the 12.5% soil moisture capacity. The least leaf area ratio for *M. tomentosa* seedlings was 76.6 cm²/g recorded in the 100% soil moisture capacity. The highest specific leaf areas for *F. africana* and *M. tomentosa* were 271.4 and 1015.5 and these were observed in seedlings supplied with 50% soil moisture level. The seedlings of *Prunus africana* that were treated to 100% soil moisture capacity had the highest specific leaf area (2353.1cm²/g). The least specific leaf area (167.3, 306.9 and 327.8 cm²/g for *F. africana*, *M. tomentosa* and *P. africana* seedlings) were recorded in the 12.5, 12.5 and 50% soil moisture field levels respectively.

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Table 2. Means of growth parameters of the seedlings of three tree species under four soil moisture level.

species	Treat- ments	Mean height	Mean collar diameter	Mean leaf number	Mean total leaf area	Mean number of first order lateral roots	Mean Length of the main root	Leaf area ratio	Specific shoot length	Specific root length	Specific leaf area
	(% SFC)	(cm)	(cm)		(cm ²)		(cm)	(cm ² /g)	(cm/g)	(cm/g)	(cm ² /g)
<i>F. africana</i>	12.5	49.0	7.1	20	913	6	17.4	58.7	8.7	3.9	167.3
	25	72.4	9.9	21	1997	11	17.1	64.8	6.1	1.9	205.1
	50	88.6	11.3	31	5213	15	17.3	86.5	3.6	1.1	271.4
	100	82.4	11.3	22	3276	13	27.3	60.3	4.1	1.4	214.6
<i>M. tomentosa</i>	12.5	46.7	9.5	36	3331	6	15.2	120.4	6.8	1.5	306.9
	25	62.0	10.9	42	10713	11	36.5	267.1	6.1	2.1	858.4
	50	49.7	12.1	40	6313	8	49.0	137.4	4.8	1.7	1015.5
	100	49.6	17.8	36	3233	11	41.2	76.6	4.9	1.6	481.8
<i>P. africana</i>	12.5	36.8	4.3	16	116	5	23.8	94.9	60.4	59.3	476.0
	25	41.9	3.5	16	176	5	22.3	107.6	44.9	46.2	758.9
	50	31.1	3.4	14	137	4	20.9	99.5	50.2	59.0	327.8
	100	55.7	4.3	13	370	8	23.9	143.1	36.8	30.7	2353.1
	Mean	54.5	9.5	27	3352	11	26	125.0	16.4	13.6	666.9
	LSD (0.05)	7.0	1.4	4	524	3	7.1	41.6	22.9	23.0	1108.7
	FPr.	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.85	0.47	0.05

Where LSD=Least square difference, %SFC= Percentage soil field capacity and Pr is the variance probability.

3.3 The effects of soil moisture levels on biomass components of seedlings of three native tree species

The effects of treatments on the biomass components of seedlings were highly significant ($P \leq 0.001$) (Table 3). The seedlings of *Funtumia africana* treated with 50% soil moisture capacity had the highest leaf biomass (19.3g), stem biomass (24.7g), total biomass (60.3g). The species with the highest root biomass (29.3g) was *Markhmia tomentosa*. The least leaf biomass (0.2g), stem biomass (0.6g), root biomass (0.3g) and total biomass (1.1g) were observed with *Prunus africana* seedlings treated with 12.5% soil moisture capacity. The leaf mass fraction and root shoot ratio were highly significantly different with respect to treatments while the shoot and root mass fractions for the seedlings did not show significant differences.

The root biomass of *Markhmia tomentosa* seedlings was greater than the shoot biomass and therefore the root/shoot ratios were greater than 1.0 (Table 3). The seedlings of *F. africana* supplied with soil moisture at field capacity also allocated more biomass to the roots than the shoots. The seedlings of *Funtumia africana* and *Markhmia tomentosa* supplied with 12.5% soil moisture level recorded the highest leaf mass fraction (0.4 g/g). The seedlings of *M. tomentosa* and *P. africana* supplied with 50% soil moisture level and seedlings of *P. africana* treated with soil moisture at field capacity had the least leaf mass fraction of 0.1 g/g. The seedlings of *M. tomentosa* supplied with 50% soil moisture capacity recorded the highest root/shoot ratio (2.8 g/g) while seedlings of *Prunus africana* treated with 25% soil moisture capacity recorded the least root/shoot ratio of 0.4 g/g (Table 3).

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Table 3. Means of biomass components of seedlings of three native tree species under four soil moisture levels.

Species	Treatments (%SFC)	Mean leaf biomass (g)	Mean stem biomass (g)	Mean root biomass (g)	Total biomass (g)	Leaf mass fraction (g/g)	Shoot mass fraction (g/g)	Root mass fraction (g/g)	Root shoot ratio (g/g)
<i>F. africana</i>	12.5	5.5	5.6	4.5	15.6	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.8
	25	9.7	11.9	9.1	30.8	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.8
	50	19.3	24.7	16.3	60.3	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.7
	100	15.3	20.0	19.1	54.4	0.3	0.4	0.4	1.0
<i>M. tomentosa</i>	12.5	10.9	6.9	9.9	27.7	0.4	0.2	0.4	1.4
	25	12.5	10.1	17.5	40.1	0.3	0.3	0.4	1.7
	50	6.2	10.4	29.3	46.0	0.1	0.2	0.6	2.8
	100	6.7	10.1	25.4	42.2	0.2	0.2	0.6	2.5
<i>P. africana</i>	12.5	0.2	0.6	0.3	1.1	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.6
	25	0.3	1.1	0.5	1.9	0.1	0.6	0.3	0.4
	50	0.5	0.7	0.4	1.6	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.5
	100	0.3	1.5	0.8	2.6	0.1	0.6	0.3	0.5
	Mean	7.3	8.6	11.1	27.0	0.3	0.4	0.4	1.1
	LSD	0.4	0.4	0.1	0.7	0.1	0.1	0.03	0.1
	FPr.	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Where LSD=Least square difference, %SFC= Percentage of soil moisture compared to field capacity and Pr = the variance probability.

3.4 Rate of transpiration, evapotranspiration and water use efficiencies of the species

The mean temperature, light intensity and relative humidity during this experiment were 29.9°C, 275000 lux and 64% respectively. The minimum temperature (24°C), light intensity (73000 lux) and relative humidity (56%) were also recorded. The maximum temperature (33.5°C), light intensity (497000 lux) and relative humidity (71%) were noted. Rate of transpiration calculated for *F. africana* was 2.29 gH₂O/s/m², *M. tomentosa* (12.69 gH₂O/s/m²) and *P. africana* (0.51 gH₂O/s/m²) were significantly different ($P = 0.03$) for the different species (Figure 4a). The rates of evapotranspiration recorded with *F. africana* was 10.76 gH₂O/s/m², *M. tomentosa* (14.2 gH₂O/s/m²) and *P. africana* (0.73 gH₂O/s/m²) were significantly different for the different species (Figure 4b). Water-use efficiencies were significantly different ($P \leq 0.001$) with values of 176.5, 227.5 and 3692.3 ml/g recorded for *F. africana*, *M. tomentosa* and *P. africana* respectively (Figure 4c).

Figure 4.a) Rate of transpiration, b) rate of evapotranspiration and c) the water use efficiencies of the various studied tree species seedlings. S.E= Standard error

4. DISCUSSION

Soil moisture availability and plant water-use efficiency are important drivers of both vegetation cover and water-table dynamics in water catchment areas (Gonzalez-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2010). A comparison of tree seedlings for afforestation of water catchment areas under different moisture levels is especially important in the context of water catchment restoration ecology in which appropriate selection of species is critical to both the success of the afforestation/reafforestation project and the health of the environment. The early growth performances with respect to heights and collar diameters have important ecological implications in seedling establishment in the field (Egbe *et al.*, 2013). The seedlings with 50 and 100% soil moisture had adequate water for the various biochemical processes taking place in the plants such as photosynthesis and respiration. The dependency of the tree seedlings on high water availability suggested that the three species at the early growth stage have a high water requirement for growth.

These results are consistent with the findings of (Cernusak *et al.*, 2007; Gonzalez-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2010; Egbe *et al.*, 2013) who reported enhanced higher growth of these parameters in many tropical tree seedlings grown in soil moisture levels between 50-100% compared to those growing under water stress conditions. Similar results with tree species showing improved growth performance in the wet season as compared to the dry season in tropical tree seedlings has been reported (Siam *et al.*, 2008). In this light, some authors remarked that tree seedlings in wet plots showed enhanced growth compared to those grown in drought plots (Engelbrecht and Herz, 2001; Ripullone *et al.*, 2009). These findings all re-iterated the fact that water is essential for plant growth and development.

The poor growth performance of *P. africana* can be attributed to the fact that it is a high altitude plant (900-3400 m) that requires a moderate mean daily temperatures of 18-26°C (Orwa *et al.*, 2009). This explanation suggests that plant growth integrates environment and physiology to achieve its morpho-ecological functioning. The physiology of trees is controlled by biochemical, physiological as well as leaf anatomical features expressed through the morphological adjustments of the parameters. The well developed roots of *Markhmia tomentosa* corroborates a research finding that attributed drought resistant in *Eucalyptus sp.* to deep rooting ability (Otieno *et al.*, 2004). The results are not consistent with the findings of Martinez-Berdeja *et al.*, (2008) on Cactus species (*Mammillaria pectinifera*, *Obregonia denegrii* and *Coryphantha wedermanii*) whose growth performance remained either unchanged or reduced in the control (100% soil moisture level) as compared to other treatments since cactus species are drought adapted species. According to (Ripullone *et al.*, 2009), the greater root/shoot ratio of *M. tomentosa* in all the treatments indicates that this species allocates more biomass to the roots for proper establishment where there is less competition for

light resource. It may also be a genetic factor for this species. This is in contrast to root/shoot ratios of *F. africana* which was less than 1.0 which is an indication that more biomass was in the shoot than roots. This species might require additional treatment to develop a better root system while *Prunus africana* might require the best irrigation practice and climate related to altitude to do so.

The current study showed that number of leaves, leaf area and biomass can be morphological expressions of water use efficiency (Bunker and Carson, 2005). The water-use efficiencies of the tree seedlings are similar to results recorded in three tropical tree seedlings; *Albizia ferruginea* (1173 ml/g), *Eucalyptus grandis* (2388 ml/g) and *Erythrina excelsa* (2349 ml/g) (Egbe *et al.*, 13). *Eucalyptus* plantations establishment in water catchment areas have important ecological implications related to their short rotations of 7 - 10 years as this possess potential risk of water and nutrient deficiencies in catchment areas (Zahid and Nawaz, 2009). Studies on water-use efficiencies indicate that an extravagant water use through high rate of transpiration may be indicative of a species' poor potential to produce biomass as observed in *Erythrina excelsa* (Whitehead and beadle, 2004). The higher water use efficiency of *Funtumia africana* and *Markhmia tomentosa* corroborates with the finding that the lower the rate of transpiration, the higher the water-use efficiencies in a seedling (Whitehead and beadle, 2004; Ripullone *et al.*, 2009; Zahid and Nawaz, 2009). The significantly higher rate of transpiration of *Markhmia tomentosa* can be attributed to its significantly higher leaf area. This observation suggests that there is a wide variation in the morpho-genetic potentials of tree seedlings that can be exploited to rehabilitate degraded water catchment areas in Cameroon. The rate of evapotranspiration for the seedlings was significantly higher than the rate of transpiration. This is in line with some authors who observed that the transpiration rates of many tropical seedlings were less than the evapotranspiration rates (Ripullone *et al.*, 2009; Zahid and Nawaz, 2009; Zhang *et al.*, 2003). The ecological implication is that deforested ecosystem loss more water through evaporation from exposed soil than areas occupied by trees (Wright and Muller, 2006).

5. CONCLUSION

This study shows that best height, collar diameter, leaf number, root development and biomass accumulation increments of tree seedlings are achieved when there is adequate moisture (50-100% soil moisture capacities). *Funtumia africana* seedlings had better water-use efficiency in the nursery than *Markhmia tomentosa* and *Prunus africana* seedlings. This, together with better root development makes *F. africana* and *M. tomentosa* better species for the reforestation/afforestation of water catchment areas in Cameroon to replace *Eucalyptus* species. A long term field study would be necessary to determine the ecological attributes of these species at maturation and the effect of tree density in a water catchment area. *Prunus africana* is a montane forest species and should be evaluated for water catchments at elevations of at least 900 m above sea level as its potential physiological attribute can be exploited.

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